

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

No. 62 - June 2019 · www.ioc-unesco.org/hab

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

The 18th International Conference for Harmful Algae

Twenty five years after the 6th *International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton* (6th ICHA, 1993), experts on harmful algal blooms and phycotoxins met again in Nantes, the beautiful capital of the Loire-Atlantique, to participate in the 18th *International Conference on Harmful Algae* convened by ISSHA. The conference was hosted by IFREMER, France from 21st to 26th October 2018. The local organizing committee was chaired by **Philipp Hess**, with the support of the French PHYCOTOX society.

As in 1993, this event was held in the Conference Centre at the Cité des Congrès, a few minutes' walk from the Château des Ducs de Bretagne, a major landmark in the city. For HAB experts, particularly those interested in *Dinophysis*, Brittany and the Loire-Atlantique region with the Loire and Vilaine river estuaries, is famous for being a hot spot of *Dinophysis* and DSP outbreaks in western Europe. That was the focus of Patrick Lassus, the local organizer of the HAB conference in 1993, when he coined the term "*Dinophysis acuminata* complex" to label a continuum of cell morphotypes difficult to ascribe to *D. acuminata* or to *D. sacculus*, recently re-

viewed in the monograph by Lassus et al. (Fig. 1). Participants were welcomed on Sunday evening with an ice-breaker at La Cité (Fig. 2), and got a taste of the local gastronomy and traditions during the Bretonne Party on Tuesday night (Fig. 3). They were taken again on board a boat along the Erdre River for the Conference Dinner, this time at the Château de la Poterie.

The 18th ICHA, had the largest participation of all ICHA's to date with 709 delegates from 64 countries registered. This exceeded the record from the 10th ICHA in St Pete's Beach, Florida, 2002. Gone are the old days when all of the oral contributions were given in plenary sessions. At the 18th ICHA, delegates had the program, downloaded onto their mobile phones, and selected their presentation of choice from two or even three parallel sessions. The theme of the 18th ICHA conference was "From Ecosystems to Socio-Ecosystems". Delegates were kept busy over the five days with three parallel sessions containing 45 ignite talks, 255 oral presentations and 358 poster presentations. This was a lot of hard work for the local organizers (Fig. 4) and the Scientific Steering Committee. In the background, IS-

Fig. 1. Drs Philipp Hess (left) and Patrick Lassus (right), from IFREMER, Nantes, local organizers of the 18th ICHA (2018) and 6th ICHA (1993) respectively, signing copies of their monograph (see book on the right) during the conference in Nantes, 21-26 October 2018.

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Fig. 2. Ice-breaking at “La Cité”, Nantes, during the 18th ICHA, 2018

Fig. 3. Live Folk music for the participants during the conference “Bretonne Party”

SHA society members were kept very busy, fully engaged with the evaluation of student presentations to choose the candidates for the Maureen Keller awards, the election of Yasumoto lifetime achievement awards, voting for future conference venues, new ISSHA committee elections and the popular ISSHA auction (see ISSHA’s Corner).

Philipp Hess, IFREMER, Nantes, France, Eileen Bresnan, Marine Scotland, UK & Beatriz Reguera, IEO, Spain

Fig. 4. Philipp Hess (Chair), with the French Local Organizing Committee, receiving an ovation from the conference participants during the Closing Ceremony

Scientific and social scenes from participants during the 18th ICHA, Nantes, 2018.

Scientific Highlights of the 18th International Conference on Harmful Algae

Plenary talks and Yasumoto awards

Each morning and afternoon session began with plenary speakers who covered a number of topics including: climate change impacts on inland and coastal eutrophication (Anna M. Michalek), chemical studies on toxic cyanobacteria (William Gerwick), 21st century alternative methods for 21st century safety sciences (Thomas Hartung), parasites to control HABs (Laure Guillou), trait based frameworks for understanding and predicting HABs (Elena Lichtman), cyanobacteria in Danish and Florida lakes and their response to nutrient loading reduction, biomanipulation and climate warming (Erik Jeppesen) and ciguatera risk assessment and management (Mireille Chinain). The two 2016 Yasumoto award presentations, “An emerging chemical ecology paradigm” (Allan Cembella) and “The evolution of algal toxin measurement science” (Mike Quillam) were presented on the last day.

Taxonomy

Taxonomy presentations covered a range of topics. The discovery of two classes of non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria, Melainabacteria and Sericytochromatia, using genomic data (Nico Salmaso) suggests a later evolution of photosynthetic cyanobacteria than previously considered. Efforts to establish a classification of photosynthetic cyanobacteria based of genomic data (Muriel Gugger) suggest changes to the present classification, e.g the presence of only one *Microcystis* species. Cécile Bernard reported on the diversity of cyanobacteria from an extreme environment analogous to marine paleoenvironments. A new exciting dinoflagellate belonging to the Kareniaceae was described, with differing pigment composition and containing an eyespot which is mainly seen in freshwater dinoflagellates (Kazuya Takahashi). A major fish kill in Malaysia in 2016 was studied by Chui Pin Leaw, who found it to be caused by a hitherto undescribed *Chattonella* species differing genetically from *Chattonella* species already recorded. Masao Adachi found considerable diversity in *Prorocentrum*

from Japanese waters. Among the 244 strains, which all were found to be diarrhetic shellfish toxin producers, two new species were recorded and a very high genetic diversity was observed within *P. lima*.

Carlos Eduardo Tibrica reported on the evolution of a semiautomated imaged-based identification program for *Gambierdiscus*. Sirje Sildeveer and Haifeng Gu presented detailed studies expanding current knowledge on the genetic diversity of *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* and *Azadinium poporum*, respectively. Advances in understanding the confusing taxonomy of *Ostreopsis* were presented by Helena David and Olga Carnicer. *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* was suggested to be renamed *O. rinoi*, and the “true” *O. siamensis* was suggested to belong to an unnamed clade comprising strains from the Thai type locality. Furthermore, two taxa of *Ostreopsis* were reported from Galapagos waters for the first time.

Ecology

Presentations covered the impact of herbivorous predation on domoic acid production in *Pseudo-nitzschia* (Nina Lundholm) and interspecific variability was demonstrated by the different migratory behaviour of *Dinophysis* in the Ria de Vigo (Beatriz Reguera). A trait based approach was applied to metabarcoding data to investigate protist functional diversity across size-fractionated coastal planktonic communities (Pierre Ramond).

New investigative approaches to address ecological questions were presented. The *Within Outlying Mean index* (WitOMI) approach was used to investigate the niches of harmful algae using the REPHY monitoring data from France (Karasiewicz), while a Gaussian mixture was used to investigate the phenology of phytoplankton blooms in the Southern Bight of the North Sea (Lefebvre).

Alexis Fisher presented information from a study in Massachusetts on how dormancy length in *Alexandrium catenella* cysts is modulated by temperature, with dormancy shorter with

colder treatments. Dormancy of cysts at 6°C, the average bottom water temperature of the Gulf of Maine, was a full year. Raffaele Siano used metabolomic analyses to investigate differences in phosphate utilization on cysts germinated from sediments up to 20 years old and compared with those from present day. The results of this study suggest an intra-specific variability of the phosphate utilization between phenotypes of dinoflagellate of different ages in Brittany.

Leonardo Guzmán showed that the exceptional blooms of *Alexandrium catenella* in Chile during summer 2018 were highly influenced by a particular suite of coastal hydrographic conditions, which led to southeast winds induced northwards physical transport of cells from northern Aysén to the southeast of Chiloé Island and their export off the fjords. These particular coastal oceanographic conditions were influenced by large scale climatic patterns.

Omics

The polyketide synthase (PKS) pathway in dinoflagellates was investigated (Allen Place) showing them to have two parallel pathways for making fatty acids and polyketides. Results showed the presence of a transcript does not predict formation of the protein, and homology to a model system homolog does not provide a lot of information about whether the toxin will be present in dinoflagellates.

Shaun McKinnie, John Brunson and Sara Hardardóttir presented studies investigating the synthesis pathway of domoic acid (DA). Benjamin Kramer looked at transcriptome and physiology of *Dolichospermum* in response to N and P addition.

Sylke Wohlrab investigated *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* populations in two different locations, the established population from the Baltic Sea, and a small creek in the Netherlands where the population is recently established. Results showed traits under stabilizing selection are enriched in genes that have adaptive evolution. Neutral traits show lower adaptation/evolution in genes. Trait variability in the Baltic Sea is driven by gene variants, while plasticity is more common in the Netherlands. The different adaptation strategies between the populations could potentially be due to evolutionary age.

Maria Immacolata Ferrante investigated the *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* sexual cycle and found the gene that determines the mating type in this pennate diatom. *Pseudo-nitzschia* is found globally in the Tara Oceans dataset and the genes expressed during the sexual phase can track this important but overlooked event.

Cyanobacteria

Advanced technologies for the early warning of cyanoHABs including optical detection and drones are an exciting and important field that will continue to significantly aid traditional monitoring. (Jean-François Humbert, Yi Hong; Chris Bolch; Dianne Greenfield; Bengt Karlson; Sara Imran Khan). Long term reductions in N and P has led to the mitigation of cyanoHABs (Eric Jeppesen) and changes in N, P, and CO₂ can alter toxin production (Dedmer Van de Waal, Benjamin Kramer; Declan Maxwell). Cyanobacteria can be harmful to human health (Zorigto Namsaraev; Louise Vanysacker; Bojan Sedmak; Barbara Kubickova; Lenka Šindlerová), but they can also be a source of novel pharmaceuticals. (William Gerwick). The field of Omics continues to mature, facilitating new discoveries and advancing our understanding of cyanoHAB physiology, interactions, genetic diversity and opening the door for new genera to be discovered. (Anusuya Willis; Barbara Weisbrod; Todd Miller; Yingzhong Tang; Gorenka Bojadzija; Cécile Bernard; Maxime Georges Des Aulnois; Benjamin Marie; Leonardo Cerasino; Yves Terrat; Jean-François Briand; Jennifer Jankowiak; Fatma Zohra Guellati; Alexandre Campos). An emerging and important 'Omics' is socioeconomics (Chloé L'Ecuyer-Sauvageau; Olokotum Mark).

Toxins

Nathalie Arnich presented an ANSES Opinion on Acute and Chronic Toxicity of BMAA. BMAA is neurotoxic but the causal link between exposure to BMAA and the occurrence of ALS is not proven, in the current state of knowledge. Tim Harwood presented a method for simultaneous monitoring of maitotoxin and miguatoxins in algae and fish extracts, resolving a difficult analytical challenge via tandem mass spectrometry. Mark Poli presented a novel intraperitoneal

and aerosol administration in rats to investigate the toxicity and pathophysiology of palytoxin congeners.

Ecophysiology and cellular biology of harmful algae and cyanobacteria

Angela Falciatore explored the molecular basis of responses to light in marine diatoms and found that the functional diversification of the light-harvesting complex family specialized in photo-protection (LHCXs) allows diatoms to respond to a highly variable ocean environment. Yingzhong Tang demonstrated that *Karenia mikimotoi* can produce sexual, thin walled, resting cysts which are widely distributed in the East China Sea. Irradiance seems not to have a significant effect on growth rate and toxin production for *Prymnesium parvum* in culture while nutrient limitation increases prymnesin content (Nikola Medić). Anusuya Willis observed a high variation in growth rate and toxin content between strains of *Raphidiopsis raciborskii* and this variability is also observed at a genomic level. The concentration of domoic acid in cells of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* can be predicted from the cell size by a Gaussian model which shows an increase in domoic acid production when *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* cells become gametangia (Aurore Sauvey). Martin Pfannkuchen examined different mechanisms for competition for nutrients in harmful algae from the Adriatic Sea. Stefano Accoroni showed *Ostreopsis* blooms in inorganic phosphorus limited environments may be maintained by the use of organic phosphorous through alkaline phosphatase activity. A review of the autoecology of bloom forming algae from the Gulf of California showed it is necessary to account for the interactions between species when investigating phytoplankton dynamics, for example *Gymnodinium catenatum* can be consumed by *Noctiluca scintillans* and lysed in presence of *Chattonella marina*. A variety of cyanobac-

terial toxins may co-occur at the same time in Green Bay, USA which presents difficulties with the water quality control. The detection of the anatoxin-a and saxitoxin genes is not always coincident with the presence of these toxins (Todd Miller). In Lake Taihu (China), *Microcystis aeruginosa* gene expression patterns are mainly linked to conductivity and nutrient availability (Xainming Tang). The photosynthetic activity of a toxic strain of *Microcystis aeruginosa* is decreased by metabolites produced by *Daphnia magna* but this was not observed to the same extent in the case of the nontoxic strain of *M. aeruginosa* (Gorenka Bojadzija).

Parasites

Reviewing important concepts in parasitology in order to answer the question "Can we use parasites to control HABs?" reveals that a better understanding about the dynamics of both host and parasites is needed (Laure Guillou). Caution should be taken when interpreting results obtained from network analysis of high-throughput sequencing as correlation between host and parasites interactions does not necessarily imply causality (Catharina Alves-de-Souza)

Accumulation and biotransformation of toxins

Pedro Reis Costa investigated transformation of algal toxins in the food web from Portuguese waters. Cephalopods found to be intoxicated with DA showed long term retention of the toxins. Ev-

Fig. 1. Numerous virus particles produced in the cytoplasm of a bloom-forming dinoflagellate *H. circularisquama*. Photo courtesy of Takano et al from *Viruses* 10 (10): E554 (2018).

Fig. 2. Extracellular vesicles in *Alexandrium minutum*. From left to right: Vegetative cell under light microscopy; epifluorescence microscopy showing the cell chloroplasts in red; vesicles in green due to lipid stain PKH67, and composite of the epifluorescence images, theca of the cell is in blue, chloroplasts are shown in red, stained vesicles are shown in light blue. Photo courtesy of Esther Garcés

idence of PSP toxin profile changes were observed during trophic transfer events. Top predators showed dissimilar profiles to source algae and initially contaminated organisms.

Aifeng Li presented data from outbreaks of PSP in China 2016-2017. *Mytilus galloprovincialis* converted some toxins into M toxin analogues within 7 days of contamination but these comprised a relatively small proportion of total toxins present and were transformed in the hepatopancreas of mussels and scallops. M toxins are hypothesised to have toxicities similar to C toxin analogues. M toxins also found in trace levels within *Alexandrium pacificum*. M toxin quantification is tentative as standards are not available.

John Kristoffer Andres presented data from green lipped mussels which are the primary PST vector in the Philippines. During experimental exposure a cycle of PST uptake and depuration was observed. Within the first 24 hours toxins were primarily detected in the mantle, later the highest concentrations appeared within the digestive tract. Variability across treatments in both uptake and depuration was high. During the course of the study a conversion of toxins from GTX1/4 to GTX 2/3 was observed.

Biological oceanography and limnology of HABs

This interesting session contained many presentations using observations of the distribution of HAB organisms together with observations and models of physical oceanography. These different factors all contribute to improved understanding of HAB dynamics. Investigations presented include cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic, the USA and

Brazil (Norbert Wasmund, Fabiola Martins), *Phaeocystis* in the English channel (Arnaud Louchart), *Dinophysis* in Sweden, Spain, Scotland and Ireland (Bengt Karlson, Paul Dees, Robin Raine), *Azadinium* and AZA in Ireland (Stephan Mcgirr), *Pseudo-nitzschia* in Chile and the USA (coast of California) (Maximo Frangopulos, Holly Bowers), *Alexandrium* in Chile and in the USA (Oscar Espinoza-Gonzalez, Leonardo Guzman, Mike Brosnahan), *Karenia brevis* in the Gulf of Mexico (Richard Stumpf), dinoflagellate cysts in Morocco (Chaira Karima), *Microcystis* and microcystins in a New Zealand lake (Barbara Weisbrod). Presentations focusing on modelling and prediction used Individual Based Model combined with observations based on satellite ocean colour to examine *Karenia brevis* in the Gulf of Mexico (Darren Henrichs), Operational tools in Galicia, Spain (Yolanda Pazos), *Dinophysis* in the Shetland Islands (Paul Dees). Novel automated methods were used in a detailed study of *Pseudo-nitzschia* in Monterey Bay (Holly Bowers), high temporal resolution studies of HAB using the Imaging Flow Cytobot in the Baltic, the Skagerrak and in the USA (Bengt Karlson, Kaisa Kraft), machine learning and imaging (Guillaume Wacquet), high biomass blooms studied using multi-wavelength fluorometry, PAM and Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometry (Katharine Perri) and enhancement of water temperature by dense dinoflagellate blooms (Mary Ruiz-de la Torre).

Major events and long term time series

Presentations dealt with time series up to 30 years long from France (Catherine Belin), the North Sea (Callum Whyte), Canada (Nicky Haigh), Chile (Benjamin

Suarez-Isla) and Asia (Satoshi Nagai) with a number of presentations from fresh waters including canine fatalities in a Berlin lake (Jutta Fastner), toxic benthic cyanobacteria from France (Isidora Echenique-Subiabre) and a review of an outbreak of Haff disease in Russia (Zorigto Namsaraev).

A variety presentations utilising new technologies to investigate HABs included looking at qPCR methods to screen for cyanotoxins (Mark Van Asten), a combination of satellite algorithms and biogeochemical Argo floats to investigate green *Noctiluca* blooms in the Arabian Sea (Vera Trainer) and a microscopy and next generation sequencing approach to investigate waste water treatment (Arash Zamaydi).

Ciguatera and Benthic HABs

A wide ranging and diverse suite of oral and poster presentations relating to benthic HABs and ciguatera were presented over three sessions. A range of topics were addressed covering toxin extraction improvements (Mika Nagae) to CTX detection kits (Takeshi Tsumuraya), to the description of two new *Gambierdiscus* species. Food web toxin transfer paths e.g. in marine invertebrates (Taiana Darius) and the influence of habitat complexity in species composition (Po Teen Lim) are important new areas of research. New efforts to raise awareness of ciguatoxin poisoning among medics in French Polynesia will serve as a model for other endemic areas (Mélanie Tranchet).

Socio Economics

From fishermen's statements on the devastation of whole communities in the Pacific Northwest of the US (Stephanie Moore) to a trip through the Cold

Copepodamides

Fig. 3. Co-evolutionary arms race. Diatoms sense presence of copepods via presence of chemical cues (copepodamides), and respond by producing domoic acid which then affect the copepods (reduced escape response). Photo courtesy of Nina Lundholm.

War (Pat Tester) the socio economics session was as diverse as the algal genera causing the problems. Four of the six presentations made were focused on water and resource management and one included citizens monitoring efforts to provide data from African lakes (Mark Olokotum). Cyanobacteria blooms factored heavily in the choices citizens of Quebec made for the quality of their recreational areas (Chloé L'Ecuyer-Sauvageau). Most believed that the government was responsible for the resolution of cyanobacteria blooms. Water quality alert systems using satellite data went beyond the static economic loss to determine the number of fishing/shellfishing bans, mapping the risk of closures from October to December along the French Coast. This provides fishermen the opportunity to

relocate to different fishing areas or change gear for another fishery (Pascal Raux).

Global HABs and Climate Change

Research towards predicting the impact of climate change on HABs has progressed from single factor growth experiments (e.g. temperature, pCO₂) with limited HAB strains, to paying due attention to genetic population diversity (Wayne Litaker) and even work with sediment revived culture strains of different ages (Raffaele Siano). High pCO₂ increases cellular toxicity in many HABs, e.g., *Karlodinium* (Nayani Vidyaratna), but a sound working hypothesis of causative mechanism is still lacking. Field work is focusing on learning from extreme events- ENSO 2015-16

“hot blob” and Chile salmon mortality; 2017 US summer cyano blooms (Gregory Boyer), heatwaves, climate and ciguatera habitat hot spots. Modelling efforts are increasing in complexity also focusing on changes in habitat suitability (Anke Kremp), precipitation and nutrient delivery, and even including the role of mixotrophy (Patricia Glibert). Solid global HAB data bases are gradually building up using HAEDAT and OBIS platforms, and notably the efforts by PICES, ICES, FANSA, IAEA working groups. HAB time series analysis approaches are becoming more sophisticated (Chris Gobler, Catherine Belin). Not surprisingly, no single answer is emerging as to whether HABs are /will be increasing or decreasing (Gustaaf Hallegraeff), but this should be examined on a species-by-species, case-by-case, site-by-site basis.

Fig. 4. A. Student researcher placing a battery-powered personal air sampler underneath a lifeguard chair, connected to a filter house attached to the top. B. Stainless steel filter house, connected to a diaphragm membrane vacuum filtration pump hidden inside a beach cabin at the Belgian coast (Ostend). Courtesy of Maarten De Rijcke.

There were six presentations that were flagged by many during the conference.

Yoshihito Takano gave a presentation on the viral infection of *Heterocapsa circularisquama* by a HcDNAV virus. Visualisation of these HcDNAV virions using field emission scanning electron microscopy showed the virions to have a characteristic vertex lump. Most virions were observed to be absorbed on the transverse groove of the *Heterocapsa* host cells. The presence of a potential viroplasm could be observed beside the host nucleus 11 hours post infection which enlarged with time (Fig. 1). A video showing the dissection of the *Heterocapsa* cell to remove the nucleus earned a spontaneous round of applause from the audience. Sequencing of the HcDNAV virus is in progress.

Esther Garcés presented an investigation into extracellular vesicles (EV)

Fig. 5. IAEA Technical Cooperation project: the Caribbean team having a coordination meeting with the boss.

produced by *Alexandrium minutum* and demonstrated that these EVs were produced in laboratory cultures and *in situ* bloom conditions. The EVs appeared adhered to the cell surface of *A. minutum* cells during incubation experiments but it was not clear if they incorporated them into their cells (Fig. 2). There is ongoing work to identify the composition and functions of the EVs.

Nina Lundholm showed how copepodimides, polar lipids produced by copepods, induced DA production in *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* cells. All herbivorous copepods tested induced toxin production, whereas carnivorous copepods did not, supporting the theory that the toxin production in diatoms evolved as an inducible defence. However not all diatom strains tested were induced to produce DA by the presence of copepodimides. The escape response of two arctic copepods was reduced after eating DA containing diatoms but the two species were not affected in the same way (Fig. 3).

Pat Tester presented a history of STX and the Cold War which began when a contract for clams containing STX and a shipping receipt to the US Army's Biological Warfare Laboratories at Camp Detrick in the 1950s was unearthed while scanning in 'lost' PSP data from

Alaska. STX was being trialled to replace the L-cyanide pill issued to agents during WWII and a dollar with a pin impregnated with STX was issued to Gary Powers who was shot down over Russia in 1960 and exchanged at the 'Bridge of Spies' in Berlin.

Maarten De Rijcke developed a marine aerosol reference tank (MART) which allowed the concentration of toxins in sea spray aerosols (SSAs) to be quantified (Fig. 4). This facilitated the detection and quantification of OA, DTX1 and hYTX in the coast of the Southern North Sea.

Thomas Larsen presented an elegant study examining the chemical diversity of prymnesins by sequencing different strains of *Prymnesin parvum*. This showed that while individual strains produce exclusively A, B, or C-type prymnesins, the chemodiversity was great with more than 100 analogues detected. There was a random geographic distribution of A, B and C prymnesins across the globe however correlation between geno- and chemotype in microalgae was shown for the first time.

The review of the conference science would not have been possible without the valuable help of an army of reviewers:

- Elisa Berdalet & Esther Garcés, ICM (CSIC), Barcelona, Spain,
- Dave Clarke, Marine Institute, Galway, Ireland
- Tim Davis, Bowling Green State University, USA
- Margarita Fernandez-Tejedor, IRTA, Tarragona, Spain
- Chris Gobler, Stony Brook University, USA
- Maarten De Rijcke, Flanders Marine Institute, Belgium
- Gustaaf Hallegraeff, University of Tasmania, Australia
- Bengt Karlson, SMHI, Sweden
- Raphael Kudela, University of California, USA
- Adam Lewis, CEFAS, UK
- Maud Lemoine, IFREMER, France
- Nina Lundholm, Natural History Museum of Denmark, Denmark
- Chris Miles, National Research Council, Canada
- Pat Tester, OceanTester, USA
- Tim Wyatt, Borreiros, Spain
- Adriana Zingone, SZN, Naples, Italy

Eileen Bresnan, Marine Scotland, UK & Beatriz Reguera, IEO, Spain

Global HABs, Global HAB Status Reporting, and Climate Change

HABs and climate change attracted a record of 139 abstracts at the Nantes Conference. Research towards predicting the impact of climate change has progressed from single factor growth experiments (e.g. temperature, pCO₂) with limited HAB strains, to paying due attention to genetic population diversity (*Alexandrium catenella* in Alaska; **Wayne Litaker**) and novel metabolic approaches with sediment revived culture strains of different ages of *Alexandrium* vs *Scrippsiella* (**Raffaele Siano**). High pCO₂ increases cellular toxicity in many HABs (e.g. *Karlodinium*; Vidyaratna and *Alexandrium catenella*; **Máximo Frangópulos**), but a sound working hypothesis of causative mechanism is still lacking.

Field work is focusing on learning lessons from extreme events such as the ENSO 2015-16 driven *Pseudo-nitzschia* west coast US “hot blob”, 2016 Chilean record *Pseudochattonella* associated salmon mortality, and 2017 US mas-

sive summer cyanobacterial blooms in the Finger Lakes (**Greg Boyer**). Other climate lessons are being derived from studying heatwaves, and identifying climate change hotspots and ciguatera hot spots.

Modelling efforts are increasing in complexity also taking into account changes in habitat suitability (for *Alexandrium ostenfeldii*; **Anke Kremp**), precipitation and nutrient delivery, and even now including the role of mixotrophy (for *Karlodinium* vs *Prorocentrum*; **Patricia Glibert**). Increasing temperatures facilitate earlier and longer persisting *Margalefidinium* (*Cochlodinium*) *polykrikoides* blooms in the US and Korea, and earlier and large *Microcystis* blooms in Lake Erie (**Chris Gobler**).

Solid global HAB data bases are gradually building up using HAEDAT and OBIS platforms, aided by the efforts by PICES, ICES, FANSA and IAEA working groups. HAB time series analyses are becoming more sophisticated

and datasets are becoming ever longer and more robust (22 years in Uruguay, **Silvia Méndez**; 30 years for the French REPHY network, **Catherine Belin**; 33 years in Philippines, **Aletta Yñiguez**; 40 years in northern Adriatic, **Martin Pfannkuchen**).

The first series of contributions resulting from the *Global HAB Status Report (GHSR)* initiative were presented in Nantes. This effort aims to settle questions on the probability of change in HAB frequencies, intensities, and range resulting from environmental changes at local and global scales. Regional HAB status reports were presented for the Mediterranean (**Adriana Zingone**), the North Atlantic (**Eileen Bresnan**), coastal waters of Ghana (**Denutsui Dzifa**), Canada (**Cynthia McKenzie**), east coast US (**Elizabeth Fensin**), Australia (**Gustaaf Hallegraeff**), New Zealand (**Enora Jaffrezic**), Latin America and the Caribbean (**Silvia Méndez** and **Inés Sunesen**).

Different regions are dominated by different seafood toxins: PSP in North America, DSP in Northern Europe, NSP in Central America (Florida), CFP in Oceania and Australia (Fig.1). Some HAB problems flare up (*Noctiluca* on the rise in Australia) and then dissipate (*Pyrodinium* in Philippines, **Aletta Yñiguez**; *Cochlodinium* in southern Korea in 2016, **Seung Ho Baeck**).

It is important to emphasize that available information in HAEDAT or OBIS on individual events varies greatly from event to event or country to country. Therefore there is no direct proportionality between recorded events and toxicity in a given region. Areas with numerous recorded HAEDAT occurrences but with efficient monitoring and management programmes (as raised in HAN 58), may have low risk of intoxications, whereas rare events in other areas may cause severe problems and represent significant health risk. HAEDAT data sets represent the compound result of HAB events as well as how human society responds to them via changes in monitoring and regulatory approaches. The incidence of ASP closures in Scotland thus was effectively reduced post 2005 by an amendment to the EU shellfish hygiene directive (EU854/2004)

SEAFOOD TOXINS BY REGION

Fig. 1. Relative abundance of different seafood toxin syndromes in different geographic regions (North West America NWA; North East America NEA; Caribbean Central America CCA; North East Europe NEU; South East Europe SEA; Mediterranean MED; North Asia NAS; Australia New Zealand ANZ; Oceania/ Tropical Pacific (PAC). Based on an analysis of 5774 HAEDAT events recorded as of 1/3/2018. Data compiled by G. Hallegraeff & L. Schweibold.

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Barcodes and long term changes in HAB distributions

Thal-ass-ee-oh-CY-ra, Key-TOSS-er-us, Pro-toe-pear-a-DIN-ee-um, Sir-A-she-um... this might be a parody of a (very short) genetic barcode or it might be gibberish. It is in fact a sample from a list of phytoplankton genera on flashcards designed to help children pronounce Latin names. Fun for the kids, perhaps. Useful? It may lead to some idiosyncratic spelling habits. As Roman poet Horace famously wrote, *Nihil est ab omni parte beatum* (there are no unmixed blessings). But let's return to barcodes.

DNA barcoding uses short standardized DNA regions, commonly parts of genes which code for ribosomal RNAs like 18S rDNA, both to identify species which bear such names and the range of functional diversity. Today it is easy to scoop terabases of meta-genomic data out of the oceans (**Cedric Bernay**, O-243). Barcoding now provides a rapid tool to survey harmful species (**Kiang Soon Hii**, P-048; **Patricia Paredes-Banda**, P-056; **Ana Baricević**, P-186), to define species boundaries and taxonomic diversity in general, and to delineate phylogenies. It is not yet fully foolproof, and the taxonomic resolution which can be achieved varies between groups and geographical regions. A more challenging application is to find ecological meaning, to look inside the black box of the microbial community, but functional roles based on genomics are slowly emerging (**Pierre Ramond**, P-063).

The Humboldt Current bathes the coasts of Chile and Peru and forms

the eastern limb of the South Pacific subtropical gyre (Fig. 1). Off Ecuador it turns west and becomes the South Equatorial Current. The East Australian (EAC) Current forms the western limb of this gyre. The circuit is completed by the West Wind Drift (Antarctic Circumpolar Current), which is shared with the Indian Ocean and South Atlantic gyres. Variations in the intensity of these currents on decadal and longer time scales are now well established [1-2], associated with changes in wind forcing, more precisely with a poleward shift of westerlies in the Southern Hemisphere [3-5]. Winds have increased since the 1950s off Peru, with a decadal signal superimposed on the longer term trend (there is also an ENSO signal). Such variations are associated with fluctuations in the yields of fisheries, partly mediated through changes in primary production and subsequent recruitment, the match-mismatch hypothesis [6].

The EAC has two branches. One branch turns east along the Tasman front towards New Zealand, the other flows southwards along the Australian coast. Intensification of the latter since the 1940s has caused it to flow farther south (7), and it now casts eddies to the east of Tasmania. Some faunal elements from further north have colonized coastal waters in eastern Australia. These include the invasive shore crab *Carcinus maenas*, and the native sea urchin *Centrostephanus rodgersii* which has created urchin barrens. Heavy fishing of lobsters, *Jasus edwardsii*, which

eat urchins may have augmented the barrens. Some plankters too have extended their ranges, in the EAC [8, 9]. Range expansions (and contractions) reflect the dynamics of population pressures and local extinctions. For HAB enthusiasts, one of the most significant aspects of these variations must be the timing of phytoplankton growth, which over a four decade period (1940s to 1980s) off Tasmania (Maria Island) varied by several months [6].

Some changes here may not be entirely due to intensification of the EAC; a short list of other possible causative agents includes introductions, eutrophication, aquaculture, and more intense exploration. Rare or cryptic species may still resist discovery. Some of these may act concurrently. The number of possible permutations of n such agents is $n!/(n-k)!$, where k is the number we eliminate from consideration. So even if we consider that two of the five agents mentioned above are implausible, we still have $5!/(5-2)! = 20$ permutations, already a lengthy agenda. Bolch & Salas [10] tackled these difficulties on the basis of rDNA barcodes and other evidence, and concluded that three HAB species in the region are introductions (*Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Alexandrium catenella*, *A. 'tamarensis'*). There are of course doubts, due in part to a longstanding habbiological tradition which maintains *Alexandrium* taxonomy in a permanent state of flux (**Sirje Sildever**, O-126; **Tomohiro Nishimura**, P-107; **Silke Wohlrab**, O-152), and also to problem with algorithms, also in flux. At least one of Bolch's isolates (ATBB01) has been given a new name, *A. australiense* [11]. The agenda lengthens.

There have been frequent suggestions in the decades following a PSP outbreak in Chile in 1972, that the *Alexandrium catenella* responsible had by the 1990s extended its range about 10° of latitude northwards, from Magallanes to Aysén and Chiloé. But cyst data and genetics do not support the hypothesis of an expansion on this time scale. Sediments in Bahía Quellón in 43° S contain cysts dating back to 1929 [12]. Regional rDNA variations of Chilean isolates are larger than expected, and rather indicate recolonization [13], in other words the plankton sampling and genetic analyses would appear to provide evidence

Fig. 1. Sketch of South Pacific Gyre, EAC = East Australian Current

of a highly dynamic biogeographical boundary. Taxonomic uncertainties exist in Chilean waters too, and more recently (2006) PSP was detected as far north as Bahía Mejillones in 23° S.

Pre-instrumental proxies indicate climate trends on secular and longer time scales. Luminescent bands in *Porites* corals show lower calcification rates due to lower salinity, and thus serve as a proxy for runoff onto the Great Barrier Reef [14]. Similarly, diatom abundance in lake varves in central Chile are proxies for rainfall there; these time series are about four and six centuries long respectively, and are largely coherent [14-15]. It is well known that as time series lengthen variance increases. The decadal changes identified in abundance and range of different *Alexandrium* species, as well as other phy-

toplankton, whether exotic or home-grown, may eventually appear, as longer records are recovered, as no more than the tip of the proverbial iceberg. Biogeographical patterns of phytoplankton and their taxonomic diversity seem to be more dynamic than hitherto expected. Barcoding is one of the best tools we have to construct detailed records of these long term changes.

References

1. Roemmich D et al 2007. *J Phys Oceanogr* 37: 167-173
2. Sifeddine A et al 2008. *Progr Oceanogr* 79: 190-197
3. Hill K et al 2011. *J Geophys Res* 116, C01009
4. Wu L et al 2012. *Nature Clim Change* 2: 161-166
5. England M et al 2014. *Nature Clim Change* 4: 222-227

6. Harris G et al 1987. *Mar Freshwater Res* 38: 569-590
7. Ridgway KR 2007. *Geophys Res Lett* 34, L13613,
8. Ajani P et al 2001. *Proc Linnean Soc NSW* 123: 1-22
9. McLeod DJ et al 2012. *J Plankton Res* 34: 332-337
10. Bolch CJS & Salas MF de 2007. *Harmful Algae* 6: 465-485
11. John U 2014. *Protist* 165: 779-804
12. Salgado P 2011. *Master Thesis, Universidad de Concepción, Chile*
13. Varela D et al 2012. *Harmful Algae* 15: 8-18
14. Hendy E et al 2003. *The Holocene* 13: 187-199
15. Boës X & Fagel N 2008. *J Paleolimnol* 39: 237-252

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facilitating the shucking of scallops and sale of the adductor muscle.(Fig. 2).

Not surprisingly, no single answer is emerging as to whether HABs are / will be increasing or decreasing, but this should be examined on a species-by-species, case-by-case, and site-by-site basis. A special issue of the journal *Harmful Algae* devoted to the GHSR initiative is being prepared for completion by late 2019.

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Fig. 2. Changes in the incidence of different seafood toxin syndromes in the United Kingdom between 1990 and 2017, based on the number of area codes with closure events per year. Such data sets represent the compound result of HAB events as well as changes in monitoring and regulatory approaches. Routine DSP monitoring started in 1992, ASP in 1998, AZA in 2011, while the data gap in 2005 reflects reduced monitoring in Scotland. PSP closures were more prominent in the 1990s but completely absent in 2004. DSP was most prominent in 2000, while reduced ASP post 2005 resulted from a change in monitoring strategy for *Pecten maximus* to end product testing by the shellfish processors, that facilitates shucking and sale of the adductor muscle. Data compiled by E. Bresnan.

Unprecedented bloom of the cyanobacteria *Aphanizomenon* in a coastal bay of El Salvador

Cyanobacteria bloom in marine, freshwater and estuarine ecosystems [1]. It is widely recognized that increased nutrient inputs in waterbodies may enhance cyanobacterial growth, resulting in harmful algal blooms [2-3]. In estuarine systems, blooms are enhanced by factors such as excessive nutrient loading, increased surface water temperature, persistent water column stratification, long water residence time, organic matter enrichment, and hydrodynamic and salinity anomalies [4].

Several cyanobacterial species produce toxins, such as microcystins, nodularins, cylindrospermopsin, anatoxin-a, saxitoxins, LPS, aplysiatoxins, and lyngbyatoxins, which can affect humans and animals. [5]. In El Salvador, cyanobacterial blooms have only been reported in freshwater ecosystems, and blooms in estuarine environments are more commonly caused by diatoms or dinoflagellates.

In February 2019, green water discoloration, possibly caused by an intense microalgal bloom, was reported in western Bahía de Jiquilisco, particu-

larly around La Pirraya island (Fig. 1A-B; Supplementary material 1). According to the locals, this potential bloom had started on February 16th and dead clams belonging to the genus *Anadara* were found along the coast of La Pirraya Island during the bloom period (Supplementary material 2). Concern about the impacts from this bloom increased when four piglets, less than one year old, showed signs of dizziness, disorientation and pupil dilation after eating these dead clams washed ashore La Pirraya island at low tide. These piglets subsequently died as they were not able to walk or swim when the tide rose (Supplementary material 3).

In response to this event, five sites in Bahía de Jiquilisco (Fig. 1A) were sampled on 19th by LABTOX-UES staff using a Van Dorn bottle and 20 µm phytoplankton net. Phytoplankton species were quantified using the Utermöhl method or a Sedgewick-Rafter chamber (depending on cell abundance). An additional water sample from February 18th sampled by staff from the Ministry of the Environment and Natural Re-

sources (MARN) offshore from La Pirraya island was also available for analysis.

Samples from February 18th revealed the presence of a high density population (127×10^3 colonies L⁻¹) of the cyanobacteria *Aphanizomenon* (Fig. 2). Colonies were counted since cells were moderately disintegrated and difficult to indentify individually. This species of *Aphanizomenon* presented filaments forming fascicle-like colonies that ranged from 99 to 698 µm in length and 46 to 257 µm in width.

Water temperature ranged from 30.4 to 31.1°C, pH from 7.0 to 8.1 and Secchi disk depth from 2.0 to 2.3m.

Aphanizomenon is one of the most common bloom-forming cyanobacteria reported to form blooms in brackish environments [3] and more recently anthropogenic modifications of aquatic environments. However, this genus has not been previously reported in the brackish environments of El Salvador. The genera *Dolichospermum*, *Pseudanabaena*, *Lyngbya*, and *Oscillatoria* have been recorded in Bahía de Jiquilisco, [8]. This event is the first first report of an *Aphanizomenon* bloom in the brackish environments of El Salvador.

Despite of the high concentration of *Aphanizomenon* in the sample of February 18th, the genus was not detected

Fig. 1. A. Location of La Pirraya Island and sampling point in Bahía de Jiquilisco, El Salvador. B. Sampling location in Bahía de Jiquilisco. C. Shore of La Pirraya Island, where four pigs died.

Fig. 2. *Aphanizomenon* fascicles found in Bahía de Jiquilisco observed using an inverted microscope.

Table 1. Most abundant phytoplankton genera and species found in Bahía de Jiquilisco, February 19th, 2019.

Taxa	Cell abundance (cells L ⁻¹)
<i>Coscinodiscus</i> spp.	54,429
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	44,363
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp.	18,148
<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	672
<i>Tripos fusus</i>	672
<i>Prorocentrum</i> c.f. <i>compressum</i>	336
<i>Tripos furca</i>	336
<i>Dinophysis caudata</i>	20

in the samples collected during February 19th; suggesting the bloom lasted around three days. Table 1 shows the most abundant phytoplankton genera and species found at the five sampling sites on February 19th. These species were found in similar abundances in previous reports from this area.

It is most likely that the spring high tides that occurred during the night of February 18th washed away the bloom, since local inhabitants reported that after high tide they no longer saw water discoloration. Locals of La Pirraya also expressed they had never seen such type of bloom in the area before.

Although toxicity was not measured in tissues from the dead piglets, it is suspected that the *Aphanizomenon* bloom was linked to their intoxication,

since this genus has been reported to produce toxins such as cylindrospermopsin, anatoxin-a, and saxitoxins than can cause hepatic and neurologic effects on mammals [5, 9]. Although four piglets died, there were several other pigs (1.5 years old) nearby that ate dead molluscs but did not die, and signs of dizziness and disorientation they had exhibited disappeared with time.

This event highlights the need to monitor cyanobacteria blooms in El Salvador and the toxins produced by species within this group, since the current national capability to study these blooms is low.

Acknowledgements

We thank the NGO ProCosta for their support for the sampling campaign and

providing video material, the Secretary of Scientific Research from the University of El Salvador for logistic support, and the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (MARN) for providing water samples. This work was funded by IAEA Project RLA7022 and by the “Network for the Investigation of marine coastal stressors in Latin America and the Caribbean (REMARCO)”

Supplementary material

This material was provided by NGO ProCosta and can be accessed in the following links:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1HLgwp_d9JNhZQQYedVsQVCW0oYQONvn4?usp=sharing

References

- Codd G A et al 2005. In *Harmful Cyanobacteria*, pp. 1–23
- Paerl H W & J Huisman 2018. *Science* 320: 57–58
- Paerl H W & T G Otten 2013. *Microb Ecol* 65(4): 995–1010
- Paerl H W 1996. *Phycologia* 35: 25–35
- Codd G A 2000. *Ecol Eng* 16: 51–60
- Espinoza J et al. 2013. *Bioma* :43–46
- Espinoza J et al 2013. *Atlas de Fitoplankton Marino*. http://hab.ioc-unesco.org/ANCA_documents/#70
- Cuéllar T del C & C G Rivera 2010. *Universidad de El Salvador*, 2010, pp. 59–81
- Ballot A et al. 2013. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 76(4) 1173–1180

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Dinoflagellate toxins recorded during an extensive coastal bloom in northern Chile

Harmful algal blooms (HABs), commonly known as red tides, are primarily caused by the accelerated growth of phytoplankton due to a variety of oceanographic factors. Dinoflagellates and diatoms are often the phytoplankton groups associated with HABs [1-2]. In the present study we investigated a coastal bloom occurring along the city of Antofagasta, located on Atacama Desert, Chile. This particular bloom began in late November 2018 and continued into February 2019. The bloom extended more than 30 kilometers from the coast to the open ocean and over 600 kilometers along the coastline from the northernmost Chilean city to the south of Antofagasta. This bloom expanded even more in 2019, to approximately 1,500 kilometers in length, reaching the coast of Peru near Arequipa city. A NASA WorldView platform was established to monitor chlorophyll *a* fluorescence on a daily basis from December 2018. Chlorophyll *a* values estimated by this platform remained over 10 mg/m³ until the beginning of March 2019 (Fig. 1). This is one of the most extensive and persistent algal blooms in Chilean history. Microalgal blooms of this scale may have

sporadically occurred in this region in the past, but their magnitude has never been investigated using satellite images of chlorophyll fluorescence. Here we studied this event and established a set of HAB monitoring methodologies to understand microalgal dynamics in this region.

Approximately 100 phytoplankton species are capable of producing toxins. Some of these toxins are harmful to humans, even resulting in fatal outcomes in developing nations (e.g. South Africa, Madagascar and Comoros, among others) [3, 4]. The causes of the different poisoning cases can be attributed to a variety of microorganisms, toxins (derivatives and analogs), and even vector organisms concentrating these compounds (e.g. puffer fish) [3, 5-6].

We collected the seawater samples from five different stations, using a boat along the coast of Antofagasta in December 2018, namely CAP, SR, PUERTO, NR, and 2ED. These samples were concentrated in two steps: First, we towed an adapted conical 20 µm mesh for approximately 100 meters from a moving boat. Secondly, the concentrated volume was again filtered in the laboratory

through a borosilicate MGA grade membrane with a 1.6 µm pore size (Munktell Ahlstrom). It should be noted that 30 mL of unfiltered water instead of 60 mL were filtered through borosilicate membrane in the case of station 2ED. Lastly, toxins were extracted from the borosilicate membrane filters with methanol, the sample extracts filtered through a PVDF membrane, pore size 0.2 µm, and the filtrates analyzed by HPLC/MS/MS. (Table 1).

Prorocentrum micans was the dominant species in all stations. Other species observed belonged to the genera *Triplos*, *Peridinium*, *Dinophysis*, *Protoperidinium*, and *Gymnodinium* (Fig. 2). Preliminary observations confirmed the presence of four of the five most reported genera of toxin producing dinoflagellates (Fig. 2, images 7-11) [3]. Interestingly, *Dictyocha* sp., a rare species in this region, was observed in some samples. High biomass blooms of this genus may be harmful to fish due to development of anoxic conditions (Fig. 2, image 3). It has been shown that *Dictyocha* spp. produce toxins, but they have not been fully characterized [7].

These dinoflagellate genera observed are in accordance with the different toxins recorded. Species within the *Dinophysis* and *Protoceratium* genera are known to be producers of pectonoxins (PTXs) and yessotoxins (YTXs)

Fig. 1. Chlorophyll 'a' estimates along the northern Chilean coast captured by satellite images. Region of Antofagasta is pointed by the red dotted square and Antofagasta city is shown by the red dot. The cell image shows *Prorocentrum* sp., the main bloom species of this HAB event. Image A shows some dead jellyfish observed at sampling points and image B shows squid from a massive squid mortality in Bahía Inglesa (coastal bay close to latitude 27° S). Satellite images were taken from Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS) and Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (NPP) satellites imagery viewer.

Table 1. Toxin concentration per sample. Toxins screened included PTX1 (pectenotoxin-1), PTX2 (pectenotoxin-2) and YTX (yessotoxin). DA (domoic acid), SPX1 (spirolide-1), GYM (gymnodimine), OA (okadaic acid), DTX1 (dinophysistoxin-1), DTX2 (dinophysistoxin-2), AZA1 (azaspiracid-1), AZA2 (azaspiracid-2), AZA3 (azaspiracid-3), 45-OH-YTX (45-hydroxy-YTX), 45-OH-homo-YTX (45-hydroxy-homo-YTX) were analyzed with no detectable amounts recorded. Each result is given in pg per cell. ND refers to “not detectable”.

Sample	Coordinates (Latitude/Longitude)	Cell count (cells/mL)	PTX1 (pg/cell)	PTX2 (pg/cell)	YTX (pg/cell)
3CAP	23° 40' 53.2757" S / 70° 25' 19.6918" W	3,252,500	0,00194	0,00950	0,00336
SR	23° 40' 04.8082" S / 70° 24' 39.9169" W	3,102,500	0,00082	0,00328	0,00240
PUERTO	23° 39' 07.6038" S / 70° 24' 34.7150" W	2,667,500	0,00153	0,00406	0,00026
NR	23° 39' 16.6949" S / 70° 24' 28.8831" W	3,482,500	0,00102	0,00606	0,00588
2ED	23° 41' 18.8641" S / 70° 25' 44.1511" W	2,547,500	0,00008	0,00446	ND

respectively. Dinoflagellate strains from the bloom samples were also isolated and established in axenic cultures. Their 8S ribosomal DNA was analyzed using conventional Sanger sequencing techniques.

The toxicity of PTXs, YTXs and analogs to humans has yet to be confirmed however these lipophilic toxins may cause cellular death, apoptosis and other damages in mouse neuroblastoma cell tests. PTXs and DSP (diarrhetic shellfish poisoning) toxins are both produced by *Dinophysis* species and often co-occur in shellfish samples. The frequent co-occurrence of DSP with PSP (paralytic shellfish poisoning) toxins in Chile, presents additional complications to the application of standard toxin detection methods [10-13].

Previous research on shellfish (bivalves, gastropods) toxins has been carried out mainly in southern Chile.

Further studies should be developed, especially on rapid-detection methods, to focus on local seafood products in northern Chile. Little is known about the toxin profiles and toxicity of shellfish in this region.. This lack of information presents a potential threat to seafood exports from Antofagasta and other high production areas in northern Chile [14].

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the use of images from the NASA Worldview application (<https://worldview.earthdata.nasa.gov/>), part of the NASA Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS) and the financial support from FONDEF Grant IT17F10001 & MACHI SATREPS.

References

1. Zohdi E & M Abbaspour 2019. *Int J Environ Sci Technol* 16: 1789

2. Kang HE et al 2018. *PeerJ* 6: e4854
 3. Tamele IJ et al 2019. *Toxins* 11(1): 58
 4. Visciano P et al 2016. *Front Microbiol* 7: 1051
 5. Silva M et al 2015. *Toxins* 7(3): 859-885
 6. Fujiki H et al 1981 *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 78: 3872-3876
 7. Maciel-Baltazar E 2015. *Hidrobiológica* 25(3): 382-389
 8. Lim AS et al 2014. *Harmful Algae* 37: 53-61
 9. Zhou Y et al 2017. *Sci Total Environ* 574: 499-508
 10. Fernández ML 2000. *S Afr J mar Sci* 22: 339-346
 11. Dell’Ovo V et al 2008. *Toxicol Sci* 106: 392-399
 12. Toyofuku H 2006. *Mar Pollut Bull* 52: 1735-1745
 13. Cañete E et al 2008. *Toxicon* 52: 541-550
 14. Alarcán J et al 2018. *Mar Drugs* 16(2): 46

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Fig. 2. Clear field microscopy image of a sample collected from station “PUERTO” during the bloom in Antofagasta in December 2018. The image shows a variety of dinoflagellates. All green arrows flag a number of different organisms groups 1. *Protoperidinium cf steinii*; 2. *Prorocentrum sp.* 3. *Dictyocha*; 4. *Thecate dinoflagellate* (possibly apical view of *Peridinium sp.*; 5. *Tripos furca*; 6. Possibly *Gambierdiscus sp.*; 7. *Prorocentrum triestinum*, 8. *Prorocentrum micans*; 9. *Dinophysis acuminata* complex. 10. *Thecate dinoflagellate* (possibly apical view of *Alexandrium sp.*; 11. *Gymnodinium sp.*; 12. *Entomoneis sp.*; 13. *Cylindrotheca sp.* The yellow arrows indicate two diatoms observed in the sample, and the red arrows indicate the remaining dinoflagellates

HABs in Paradise revisited

Fig. 1. Map of Rangitāhua/Kermadec Islands.

Over 700 kilometres to the northeast of New Zealand are the largely uninhabited Rangitāhua/Kermadec Islands (Fig. 1). The islands fall within New Zealand's exclusive economic zone and several recent expeditions have resulted in the identification of dinoflagellate genera, particularly epiphytic, harmful algae bloom (HAB) species, collected from macroalgae at depths of up to 28 m. The first expedition to collect epiphytic dinoflagellate samples was to Boat Cove, Raoul Island, in 2013, and the results were reported in a previous Harmful Algae News article [1]. The first *Gambierdiscus* species identified were from North Meyer Island, from an expedition in 2014 [2-4]. Species included *G. australes*, a novel *Gambierdiscus* species, and possibly *G. polynesiensis*. The identification of *G. polynesiensis*, however, was by morphology alone and as cul-

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of *Gambierdiscus honu*, isolated from samples collected from macroalgae in North Meyer Island, Rangitāhua/Kermadec Islands. Bar = 20µm.

tures failed to thrive and were not able to be confirmed by DNA sequencing. Maitotoxin (MTX)-1 and MTX-3 were produced by *G. australes* and MTX-3 by the unknown species as determined by liquid chromatography-tandem-mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS; Table 1) [5,6]. The novel species, which was collected from non-geniculate coralline turfs, was characterised as *G. honu* [7] (Fig. 2).

This species has also been reported from Rarotonga, Cook Islands. No MTX-1 or algal ciguatoxins (CTX-3B, CTX-3C, CTX-4A, CTX-4B) were detected by LC-MS/MS analyses, although MTX-3 was detected in extracts of *G. honu* from all sites. Interestingly, extracts of *G. honu* (CAWD242) were toxic by intraperitoneal injection to mice, but much less toxic by the oral route [7,8]. The differences in toxicity of extracts from known MTX-producers suggest the probability of an uncharacterised compound being produced and this is being investigated.

Subsequent published reports summarised the dominant dinoflagellate genera detected at Raoul Island, North Meyer Island, Macauley Island and L'Esperance Rock and the presence of *Gambierdiscus*, *Coolia*, *Prorocentrum*, *Ostreopsis* and *Amphidinium* was noted [2-6]. An isolate of *G. polynesiensis* from Macauley Island, identification confirmed by DNA sequencing, was tested for ciguatoxins but, unusually, did not produce those toxins, although it did produce MTX-3 [5]. It is noted, however, that the ciguatoxin production may have been below the limit of detection of the method, rather than a non-producer.

The *Ostreopsis* species isolated from the Kermadec Islands has yet to be described but was genetically identical to *Ostreopsis* sp. 3 [9]. One isolate, from the 2013 expedition to Raoul Island, produced detectable concentrations of a palytoxin-like compound (0.013 pg palytoxin equivalents per cell) [2] whereas another isolate of the same

species from a later expedition to North Meyer Island was non-toxic [3].

The most recent expedition was in March 2018 on the HMNZS Canterbury. Samples collected from macroalgae (Fig. 3) were mainly from *Dictyocha* sp. and resulted in many isolates of *Gambierdiscus* and the successful culture of individual cells of *Coolia malayensis*, *Ostreopsis* sp. 3 [10] and *Prorocentrum lima*. The *C. malayensis* isolate is yet to be analysed for MTXs but isolates from the Cook Islands and New Zealand (CAWD154 and CAWD175) do produce MTX-3 (unpublished data).

The only *Gambierdiscus* species isolated on this occasion was *G. australes* (species determination by DNA sequencing) and it was also the dominant micro-alga in all samples. Analyses of ciguatoxins and MTX-1 and MTX-3 (LC-MS/MS) of the four isolates indicated varying production rates of MTX-1 and MTX-3 per isolate.

The *P. lima* isolate (maintained in the CICCM as CAWD283) produced 14 pg/cell total okadaic acid and 0.5 pg/cell total dinophysistoxin-1 (DTX-1). A dinophysistoxin isomer was also detected by LC-MS/MS analysis. The LSU rDNA D1/D2 sequence of this strain was identical to those of previously reported strains, i.e., Chinese strains 2S1F7 and TIO124, a Mexican strain PL6 and strain DNS-7.

As more research is undertaken it has become clear that the *Gambierdiscus* species that have been found in the Pacific region are wide-spread and that toxin production by *Gambierdiscus* is variable within species. Isolates of *G. australes* have produced from 1 – 36 pg/cell of MTX-1 [3]. The best MTX-1 and MTX-3 producer from the 2018 trip, CAWD282, has been lodged in the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae to underpin future research and production of certified reference materials. Non-toxic *G. polynesiensis* strains, such as CAWD254 from Macauley Island, will enable further molecular research into toxin producing genes, for example using a comparative transcriptomic approach in which transcriptomes of species with contrasting toxin profiles are compared [11].

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Janet Adamson for technical support and to the curators of the

Table 1. Dinoflagellate species identified in epiphytic samples collected from Rangitāhua/Kermadec Islands, 2013-2018.

Species	CICCM+ CAWD Code	Sampling site	Macro-algal host	GenBank codes	Toxins	Reference
<i>Amphidinium carterae</i>	(N: #1 Amph)	North Meyer Is	Mixed rhodophytes	KY069056	NT	[3]
<i>A.cf. massartii</i>	222	Raoul Is	"	KM259619	NT	[2]
<i>Coolia malayensis</i>	(N: Mac#4)	Macauley Is	Non-geniculate coralline	MF109031	Not tested	[5]
<i>Gambierdiscus australes*</i>	244	North Meyer Is	Mixed rhodophytes	KY069059	MTX-1, -3	[3,8]
" "	255	Macauley Is	"	MF109033	MTX-1, -3	[5]
" "	256	"	"	MF109034	MTX-1, -3	[5]
<i>G. honu</i>	242	North Meyer Is	"	KY062662	MTX-3	[8]
<i>G. polynesiensis</i>	254	Macauley Is	Non-geniculate coralline	MF109032	MTX-3 ^a	[5]
<i>Ostreopsis</i> sp. 3	221	Raoul Is	Mixed rhodophytes	KY197854	Palytoxin ^b	[2,5]
" "	241	North Meyer Is	"	KY069060	Negative for palytoxin	[3]
" "	272	Macauley Is	"	NE	NT	Not published
<i>Prorocentrum</i> cf. <i>emarginatum</i>	228	Raoul Is	"	MF109035	NT	[2]
<i>P. hoffmanianum</i>	(N: Prorocentrum #1)	"	"	KM360089	NT	[3]
<i>P. lima</i>	283	"	<i>Dictyocha</i> sp	LC422235	OA, DTX-1	this study

*CICCM: Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae. *Many more isolates of *G. australes* have been reported but are not entered in GenBank and are not included in this table [5]. MTX: maitotoxin; CTX: ciguatoxins; N: not maintained in CICCM (original code name given); NT: non-toxic; NE: not entered in GenBank, identification by qPCR assay; ^a: no CTX produced; ^b: Palytoxin-like compounds.

Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae, Krystyna Ponikla and Sarah Challenger. Thanks also to Libby Liggins and J. David Aguirre from Massey University who collected additional algae during the HMNZS Canterbury trip. Funding for research and the collection was from the NZ Ministry for Business, Innovation and Employment (Seafood Safety programme, Contract No. CAWX1801; National Databases contract No. CAWX0902) and a Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) Overseas Research Fellowship.

10. Sato S et al 2011. *PloS ONE* 6(12): e27983
11. Rhodes L & K Smith 2018. *NZ J Mar & Freshw. Res.* (available on-line: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00288330.2018.1492425>).
12. Kohli GS et al 2017 *Eukaryotic Microbiol-ogy* 64: 691-706

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References

1. Rhodes L & K Smith K 2016. *Harmful Algae News* 53: 11
2. Rhodes L et al 2014. *NZ J Mar & Freshw Res* 48: 594-599
3. Rhodes LL et al 2017. *NZ J Mar & Freshw Res* 51: 490-504
4. Rhodes L et al. 2017. *Harmful Algae News* 56: 1-4
5. Rhodes LL et al 2017. *Mar Drug* 15(7): 219
6. Rhodes et al 2015. In: MacKenzie (ed.). *Marine and Freshwater Harmful Algae. Proc. 16th Int Conf on Harmful Algae, New Zealand October 2014*, pp 180-183
7. http://www.cawthron.org.nz/media_new/publications/pdf/2015_10/ICHA16-Proceedings.pdf
8. Rhodes L et al 2017. *Harmful Algae* 65: 61-70
9. Munday R et al 2017. *Mar Drug* 7: 208

Fig. 3. A. Shallow water reef, west side of North Meyer Island (image by Tom Trnski); B. Typical reef cover where macroalgae are abundant; C. Sargassum at Havre Rock where large, dense macroalgae grow in shallow waters (images B and C by Crispin Middleton, NIWA, New Zealand).

Epiphytic dinoflagellates from Niue, South Pacific Ocean

Fig. 1. Map of the South West Pacific Ocean with enlarged map of Niue included, showing sampling site at Avatele Beach.

Niue is a tropical island nation in the southern Pacific region, lying between the Kingdom of Tonga and the Cook Islands (Fig. 1). It is considered one of the smallest countries in the world (with a population of less than 2000) and yet is one of the largest raised coral atolls. Tourism is increasing, more than doubling from <3000 to 7000 in the decade between 2003 and 2013 [1]. Reef fish are an important source of protein, with the total annual reef finfish catch meeting approximately three quarters of the consumption needs of Niue's total island population [1].

Ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) is caused by toxins produced by *Gambierdiscus* species and has been previously reported for travellers to Niue who have eaten ciguatera contaminated reef fish. In order to determine if *Gambierdiscus* species were present, samples were collected at low tide on 18th September 2018 at Avatele Beach (lat: 19°07'36.1"S; long: 169°54'49.3"W). The method of collection has been described previously [2]. Macroalgae, in this case the segmented and calcareous chlorophyte *Halimeda* sp., were brushed to release micro-algae and the resultant debris trapped in 50 ml plas-

tic tubes or were shaken directly into the tubes already containing local seawater. Two drops of germanium dioxide were added to each tube to inhibit diatom growth. Samples were transported back to Cawthron Institute under a quarantine permit and isolates were cultured (f2/seawater, 1:3) to enable DNA sequencing and toxin testing [2].

Gambierdiscus was identified to genus level, but only one cell was observed, and it failed to thrive when isolated. However, isolates of *Ostreopsis*, *Prorocentrum*, *Coolia* and *Amphidinium* were successfully cultured. Analysis of DNA sequencing data confirmed the presence of *Ostreopsis* sp. 3 [3], *C. malayensis*, *Prorocentrum hoffmannianum* and *Amphidinium operculatum*. The *Ostreopsis* sp. 3 isolate was negative for palytoxin-like compounds as determined by LC-MS/MS [4]. One isolate has been submitted to the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Micro-algae (CICCM). The *C. malayensis* isolate was tested for maitotoxins (MTX) but was negative, although MTX-3 has been reported for other *C. malayensis* isolates [5].

Regarding CFP, an advisory from the International Association for Medi-

cal Assistance to Travellers (IAMAT) [6] suggests avoidance of reef fish over 2.7 kg and avoidance of the liver, intestine, head and roe of smaller reef fish. *Gambierdiscus* sp. was reported in Niue in 2008, although no molecular confirmation of species was able to be carried out at that time [7] and 0.4 incidences of CFP per 1000 people was reported in 1990 [8]. A reference was made to fluctuating CFPs and to a local hotspot at the Alofi Wharf being recorded in 2002 [7]. While *Gambierdiscus* was recorded from this study it was not identified to species level. However, it is hoped that further samples will be collected in the future to determine the exact source of the illnesses.

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Janet Adamson (technical support) and the curators of the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae, Krystyna Ponikla and Sarah Challenger. Funding for research and the collection was from the NZ Ministry for Business, Innovation and Employment (Seafood Safety programme, Contract No. CAWX1801; National Databases contract No. CAWX0902) and a Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) Overseas Research Fellowship.

References

1. Government of Niue 2014. Niue 5th Nat. Report to the Convention on Biological Diversity. Dept of Env, Alofi, Niue. 31pp
2. Rhodes L et al 2014. NZ J Mar Freshw Res 48: 594-599
3. Sato S et al 2011. PloS ONE 6(12): e27983
4. Selwood AI et al 2012. Toxicon 60: 810-820
5. Murray et al 2018. Harmful Algae 80: 80-87
6. <https://www.iamat.org>
7. Kronen et al. 2008. Pacific Regional Oceanic & Coastal Fish Dev Prog SPC, Nouméa. 189 pp
8. Dalzell et al. 1990. Fisheries resource survey of the Island of Niue. South Pacific Comm. Inshore Fish Res Proj and FAO South Pacific Aquacult Dev Proj 14 pp

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Fig. 2. Sampling site at Avatele Beach (left) and coastal view (right), Niue.

12th
ICMSS
México 2019

Comisión Federal para la Protección
contra Riesgos Sanitarios

12th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety

The Federal Commission for the Protection against Sanitary Risks (COFEPRIS), Mexico, is pleased to invite you to attend the 12th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS 2019) in

Ensenada, Baja California, Mexico

September 9 – 13 2019

icmss2019@cofepris.gob.mx

The ICMSS is an initiative of researchers from various international institutions, including the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), related to the safety of molluscan shellfish. It seeks to be a forum for the diffusion and discussion of advances and trends in this subject. Reknown experts from around the world will take part in the conference. Students, researchers, health authorities, producers of molluscan shellfish and interested public in this subject are welcome.

The main topics to be discussed during the conference will be:

- Sanitary control programs for molluscan shellfish.
- Sanitary classification of harvest areas.
- Pathogenic organisms for humans in molluscan shellfish
- Climate change and its effect on the safety of molluscan shellfish.
- Toxic phytoplankton and marine toxin.

For more general information of the event, please consult this [link](#).

Deadline to submit abstracts for the ICMSS 2019, July 5

The ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics 2019 Meeting

The International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) - Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC) Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD) met from the 2nd – 4th April 2019. The meeting was hosted by Dr. Wenche Eikrem at NIVA in Oslo, Norway.

Working group members continued to update the IOC-ICES-PICES Harmful Algal Event Database (HAEDAT) during 2018 and production of the ICES Harmful Algal Event status report is underway. This ICES report will form the contribution from the North Atlantic area to the IOC Global HAB Status Report. A summary of the HAEDAT data from the North Atlantic area and changes in the regional distribution of harmful algal events over the last 20 years will be made at the ICES Annual Science Conference, 9th – 12th September, Gothenburg, Sweden.

National reports revealed that HABs continued to cause a variety of problems in the ICES area during 2018. Examples of some extreme events reported included impacts from a *Karenia brevis* bloom in Gulf of Mexico. This bloom was very prolonged along the

western coast of the Florida panhandle and was associated with extensive mortalities of fish, marine mammals and seabirds, as well as human respiratory irritation and negative impacts on tourism. Cyanobacteria in the rivers flowing from Lake Okeechobee also impacted waterways in the west and east of Florida resulting in extensive scums and water discolourations. Cyanobacteria caused problems in Polish coastal waters, with an exceptional bloom resulting in the closure of many tourist beaches during the summer of 2018. In Denmark an extensive bloom of *Lepidodinium cf. chlorophorum* was observed in western coastal waters, resulting in green water discolourations. The first closure of shellfish harvesting areas in Sweden due to high concentrations of azaspiracids was enforced during 2018. Closures of shellfish harvesting areas as a result of paralytic shellfish toxins associated with *Gymnodinium catenatum* were reported from Portugal and Spain. In contrast, some countries experienced fewer impacts from HABs. For example no closures of shellfish harvesting areas were enforced due of paralytic shellfish toxins in Ireland, the south west of the UK and France during 2018.

New findings presented included an update of the use of satellite imaging to identify and assess the risk from HABs using examples from ongoing projects (PRIMROSE, SHELLeye, S-3 EUROHAB), investigations in the Netherlands into the occurrence of tetrodotoxin (TTX) in shellfish, the use of molecular methods to identify HAB species using qPCR methodologies (Ireland) and metabarcoding (Norway), investigations into the occurrence of *Nodularia spumigena* blooms in Oslofjord using sediment cores, a review of *Dinophysis* and diarrhetic shellfish toxins in Irish shellfish from 2005 to 2017 and preliminary analysis of historic phytoplankton and toxin data from Scotland. Phytoplankton images from the live stream of the Imaging Flow Cytobot in Hong Kong were also viewed.

Progress on work underway in Europe addressing issues associated ciguatera fish poisoning as part of the

Eurocigua and MIMAR projects was reported. Details of a workshop, now fully subscribed, on real time quantitative PCR to develop climate services for monitoring harmful algae blooms in their marine environment (co-sponsored by the Co-Clime project) hosted by the Alfred Wegner Institute in Bremerhaven in October 2019 was presented. As WGHABD is co-sponsored by the IOC, the WG was invited to complete an informal survey to inform the development of the Science Plan for the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. More information about UN Decade can be found at <https://en.unesco.org/ocean-decade>.

Studies underway on Polar HAB species included results from investigations from Greenland and Iceland. Preliminary results were presented from new projects focused on polar HABs e.g. TaXMarc (Norway), Arctic PRIZE (UK) and a dedicated cruise planned to the Arctic in 2020 (Sweden). As a result of the growing interest in polar science to identify and understand impacts from climate change, this term of reference will be carried over to next year's meeting to allow further results to be presented.

The next WGHABD meeting, 2 – 4th March 2020, will be hosted by Dr. Hanne Mazur from Institute of Oceanography in Sopot, Poland. The meeting will be held jointly with the ICES -IOC Working Group on Ballast and Other Ship Vectors (WG BOSV) and ICES WG Introduction and Transfer of Marine Organisms (WG ITMO) with Wednesday 3rd March being a shared day between the three working groups. During the 2020 meeting WGHABD will also present national reports and new findings, review progress with new technologies to identify HABs particularly in operational settings, update and discuss future work with HAB event data, provide updates on incidences of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) and associated efforts on research and prevention and present any relevant updates relating to HABs

Participants in the ICES-IOC WGHABD 2019 meeting

Continued on next page

Intergovernmental Panel convenes to set priorities for international cooperation on mitigating the effects of Harmful Algae

The Fourteenth Session of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB) was held at UNESCO Headquarters, Paris, from 24th to 26th April 2019.

The Panel reviewed actions completed during the intersessional period and set priorities for 2020-2021. The focus for 2020-2021 will be on capacity building; facilitating further development of early detection, warning and forecasting of harmful algal events; continuing the development of a periodic Global Harmful Algal Bloom Status Re-

port; implementing a Global UN Inter-Agency Ciguatera Strategy for improved research and management; guidance on harmful algae and desalination of seawater; international coordination of biotoxin monitoring, management and regulations; guidance on algal taxonomy; and on better understanding of the relationship between harmful algae and fish kills.

The Panel also reviewed activities at a regional level taking into account differences in support for the various

groups and networks and affiliation to regional IOC subsidiary bodies.

Dr. Joe Silke (Ireland) was elected as Chair and Dr. Alexandra Silva (Portugal) was elected as Vice-Chair.

The Executive Summary, Decisions and Recommendations are available [here](#).

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Participants in the XIV IPHAB meeting, UNESCO, Paris

Continued from p. 20

and the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive.

WGHABD welcomes new members at any time and is open to experts from all IOC Member States. HABs are a global problem and experts from outside the ICES region interested in joining

the WG (at own expense) are particularly welcome. WGHABD will be setting terms of reference for a new three year reporting cycle at the 2020 meeting. Now is your chance to get involved. For further information please contact the WGHABD chair or the IOC.

Authors

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GlobalHAB and the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)

GlobalHAB webpage (www.globalhab.info)

On 1st January 2016, the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (adopted by world leaders in September 2015 at an historic UN Summit) officially came into force. Over the next fifteen years, with these new Goals that universally apply to all, countries will mobilize efforts to end all forms of poverty, fight inequalities and tackle climate change, while ensuring that no one is left behind. The United Nations has proclaimed a Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030) to support efforts to reverse the cycle of decline in ocean health. It aims to gather ocean stakeholders worldwide behind a common framework that will ensure ocean science can fully support countries in creating improved conditions for sustainable development of the Ocean. The Decade will provide a 'once in a lifetime' opportunity to create a new foundation, across the science-policy interface, to strengthen the management of the ocean. The Sustainable Development Goals are a call for action by all countries – poor, rich and middle-income – to promote prosperity while protecting the planet.

How can GlobalHAB contribute to these important UN goals?

In the broader picture GlobalHAB contributes to improved management of

HABs as an ocean hazard through improved preparedness and early warning systems contributing to UN Sustainable Development Goal 11, target 11.5 and Priority 4 and Global target 7 of the Sendai Framework on Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR) 2015-2030.

GlobalHAB is contributing to these goals because it was born as a bottom-up initiative from the international community to coordinate research on HABs. The GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan integrated the most relevant objectives and pressures identified by the researchers to progress understanding, prediction and if possible, mitigation of the negative impacts of HABs on the environment, human health and wellbeing. To address these objectives some activities were listed in the GlobalHAB Plan and are already on going in different countries and regions, being led by national and international research teams and supported by different funding sources. **GlobalHAB can endorse all the research that contributes to the implementation of the GlobalHAB Plan, particularly initiatives facilitating international coordination.** Information on the procedure and application process for endorsement is available in the GlobalHAB webpage (<http://www.globalhab.info/about-us/get-involved>).

Why seek endorsement from GlobalHAB?

GlobalHAB provides an international structure for planning and coordination of international scientific activities relating to HABs. In addition, GlobalHAB provides a framework for national and regional projects to (1) coordinate their activities and, (2) participate in coordinated research, observation, and modelling initiatives focused on HABs. The GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) may endorse projects which have already been funded, project proposals prior to submission for funding, or even letters of intent. The primary criterion for endorsement is applicability to any of the GlobalHAB Science Plan objectives. Endorsement from GlobalHAB can support justification and resources for international standardization and intercalibrations of sampling methods, observations, modelling, and toxin quantification worldwide. It can assist researchers and agencies to secure funding via letters of support and endorsement for research proposals and initiatives; support communication of information about HABs to managers, policymakers and the public. It can; facilitate the establishment of links with other relevant international programmes and related projects also endorsed by GlobalHAB; and disseminate project information through newsletters, websites and other communication mechanisms.

GlobalHAB International Coordinated Activities

Some international coordinated activities listed in the Science and Implementation Plan are being led by the GlobalHAB SSC because their implementation depends on international coordination and funding. The SSC has assumed this responsibility for their implementation, with the ultimate aim to serve **the international community, which is invited to participate**. Activities include:

June 10-11, 2019

Initiated within GEOHAB (lead by Grant Pitcher and Raphael M. Kudela), GlobalHAB included fostering research on the potential links between ocean deoxygenation and HABs through interaction with IOC GO2NE (Global Ocean Oxygen Network, <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/natural-sciences/ioc-oceans/sections-and-programmes/ocean-sciences/global-ocean-oxygen-network/>). A joint GO2NE - GlobalHAB workshop is being organized in Paris, 2019 to identify potential research on this topic, to coincide with the next GO2NE workshop (http://hab.ioc-unesco.org/index.php?option=com_oe&task=viewEventRecord&eventID=2469).

Scientists interested in the topic can contact Grant Pitcher (GrantP@nda.agric.za) and Raphael M. Kudela (kudela@ucsc.edu).

October 17-19, 2019

An international workshop, “*Evaluating, reducing and mitigating the cost of harmful algal blooms: a compendium of case studies*”, which will be held in Victoria, British Columbia, Canada as part of the Annual Meeting of the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES). The workshop co-convenors are Drs Vera Trainer (USA), Keith Davidson (UK) and Kazumi Wakita (Japan) and it is jointly sponsored by GlobalHAB (SCOR and IOC), PICES, NOWPAP, ISSHA, NOAA, FAO and private companies. The goal of the 2.5-day workshop is to bring together international experts in economics, social sciences, and the study of harmful algal blooms (HABs) to develop a compendium of case studies to guide future research on the economic and social costs of HABs. The intent is that this compendium will identify priorities and unify methods for future collaborative assessments of HAB impacts.

More information can be found at: <https://meetings.pices.int/meetings/annual/2019/PICES/Program>. Scientists interested in the topic can contact Vera Trainer (vera.l.trainer@noaa.gov).

March 2018 to October 2019

Elisa Berdalet representing GlobalHAB at the CLEFSA project activities “*Emerging threats on human health in Europe due to climate change*”. CLEFSA is a project of the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) that explores the risks of food intoxication in future climate change scenarios. CLEFSA included aquatic

biotoxins in the European landscape. E. Berdalet is collaborating in the elaboration of Reports and documents through online communication and particular meetings.

Scientists interested in the topic can contact Elisa Berdalet (berdalet@icm.csic.es).

Fall 2019

Manual for water managers on mitigation of cyanobacterial HABs elaborated by Michele Burford and Chris Gobler. This manual will be an easy to understand document for drinking and recreational water managers on managing cyanobacterial HABs and will be available both in print and on web.

Fall 2019

A fish-killing HABs workshop is planned, co-funded by GlobalHAB, IOC UNESCO and the government of Chile. This workshop is coordinated by Leonardo Guzmán and the IOC/IPHAB Task Team on Fish-killing algae. The workshop will include: a) plenary lectures by invited experts to provide a synthesis of current state-of-knowledge and focus direction in furthering the understanding of fish-killing HABs, b) presentation of high impact case studies from Chile and other areas; c) participation of Chilean national scientists, monitoring and regulatory agencies and the local industries; d) laboratory demonstrations (if feasible). The outcomes of the workshop will be published as a book.

Scientists interested in the topic can contact Leonardo Guzmán (leonardo.guzman@ifop.cl) and Henrik Enevoldsen (h.enevoldsen@bio.ku.dk).

May 2020

Planning is underway for a workshop on “Modelling and prediction of harmful algal blooms, from event response to multi-decadal projections” to be held in Glasgow, UK. The organising committee consists of Neil Banas, David McKee, Bingzhang Chen, Paul Udom (University of Strathclyde), Bengt Karlson (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute), Keith Davidson, Dmitri Aleynik (Scottish Association of Marine Science), Clarissa Anderson (Scripps / SCCOOS), Dennis McGillicuddy (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution), Beatrix Siemerling (Marine Institute, Galway), and is also coordinating with Katja Fennel and Marion Gehlen, chairs of the Marine Ecosystem Analysis and Prediction Task Team (MEAP-TT) of the GODAE OceanView programme.

We hope to secure enough funds to invite a substantial number of early-career and developing-world scientists. A programme of summer-school-like tutorials will be woven into conference-style presentations and discussions. The draft programme is organised into four parts:

- Exploring the diversity of HAB modelling approaches
- Emerging technologies and platforms to support HAB monitoring
- Linking models, observations, and stakeholder needs
- Scaling up: the global impact of global change on HABs

Scientists interested in the topic can contact Neil Banas (neil.banas@strath.ac.uk). We would especially appreciate hearing from potential partners outside North America and Europe.

Summer 2020

Symposium on automated in situ observations of plankton. In recent years novel in situ instrumentation has been developed for automated high frequency HAB detection in near real time. Instruments for observing grazers, e.g. microzooplankton and multicellular zooplankton are also becoming available commercially. These instruments are now being adopted in research and also in monitoring programmes. The aim of the mini-symposium is to bring together experts on, and users of, in automated in situ imaging systems, novel sampling equipment etc. to present methods, recent results and to share experiences. Another aim is to carry out a comparison of results when analysing plankton communities quantitatively. Young scientists are one target group of the symposium. After the main symposium a young scientist’s data workshop for data processing and report/article writing is planned. The symposium is planned on summer 2020, pending the results of several applications for funds, besides some potential support from GlobalHAB. Scientists interested in the topic can contact Bengt Karlson (Bengt.Karlson@smhi.se).

GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee members

Elisa Berdalet, Institute of Marine Sciences, CSIC, Spain, Chair
Raphael Kudela, University of California, Santa Cruz, USA, Vice-chair
Neil S. Banas, University of Strathclyde, United Kingdom
Michele Burford, Griffith University, Australia
Christopher J. Gobler, Stony Brook University, USA
Bengt Karlson, Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Sweden
Po Teen Lim, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Lincoln Mackenzie, Cawthron Institute, New Zealand
Marina Montresor, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Italy
Kedong Yin, Sun Yat-Sen (Zhongshan) University, China

Eileen Bresnan, Marine Scotland Science, United Kingdom, ICES representative
Keith Davidson, The Scottish Association for Marine Science, United Kingdom, Ex-officio
Vera L. Trainer, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, USA, IS-SHA and PICES representative
Joe Silke, Marine Institute, Ireland, IPHAB representative

Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC UNESCO/ IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Ed Urban, Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research, USA

Do you have initiatives that contribute to the implementation of the GlobalHAB Scientific Programme with an international coordination perspectives?

Contact GlobalHAB @ <http://www.globalhab.info/contact>

ISSHA's Corner

The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) convened the 18th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 18), held in Nantes, France, from 21th to 26th October 2018. The ISSHA Council had two opportunistic meetings: the first before the conference on Sunday 21st October and the second after the Conference, on Saturday 27th October in addition to the organization of the General Assembly.

Young Students Session

Following the successful experience of the first *Student Speed Networking* mini-course, held on Sunday October 9th, before ICHA 2016 in Brazil [1], a new call for a similar activity was published on the ISSHA conference website. Mentors for the *Young Investigators Workshop* this year were: **Stephanie Moore** and **Kathi Lefebvre**, from NOAA; **Mike Parsons**, Florida Gulf Coast University; **Tim Davis**, Bowling Green State University and **Harry Nelson**, Industry-

FlowCam. Thirty five participants were selected from over 100 applications. The group was composed of a mixture of students, post docs, and early career scientists. The Young Investigators Workshop allowed students and senior scientists to interact and practice brief sales pitches about their research (Fig. 1).

Travel Awards

There were 74 applications for travel awards from countries all over the world to the ISSHA Travel Award Committee. Sponsors for the awards included the Scientific Committee for Ocean Research (SCOR), the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the French Groupe de Recherche GdR-PHYCOTOX and ISSHA itself. A total of 41 students (11 from US, 6 from Europe, 11 from Latin American, 3 from Oceania and 6 from Africa) received travel support and 19

French PhD students and postdocs had their registration waived. Once more, the lively ISSHA Auction raised funds for the next conference generation of students (Fig. 2).

General Assembly, Council Elections and Venue for the 20th ICHA 2022

The ISSHA General Assembly was held on Monday 22nd October from 18.30 to 20.00, followed by a generous drink and snacks party preceding the traditional ISSHA Auction led for the third time by **Robin Raine**.

Christine Band Schmidt (Mexico) presented ongoing preparations and logistic information for those planning to attend the 19th ISSHA to be held in La Paz, Baja California Sur, México (see forthcoming events, p. 31) in October 2020. The bid from Japan presented by **Ichiro Imai** (Japan) to host the 20th ICHA (2022) in Hiroshima was chosen the conference venue in 4 years time (Fig. 3).

The 11th ISSHA General Assembly was opened by President **Vera Trainer** and minutes from the previous assembly were approved. ISSHA members had voted on-line to confirm Council officials willing to continue another term. Others had to step down after years serving the Society or changing positions in their jobs and new candidates had to be chosen. Results of the elections were given by ISSHA Secretary. Officials stepping down were Vice-president **Gustaaf Hallegraeff** (Australia), ISSHA Executive Secretary, **Anke Kremp** (Finland), and treasurer, **Henrik Enevoldsen** (Denmark) who accepted to continue his service as council member. Council members **Karen Le Bret** (Sweden), **Lincoln McKenzie** (New Zealand) and **Luis Proença** (Brazil) also stepped down. The President thanked all of them in the name

Fig. 1. The Young Students Session, ICHA 2018. Teachers (top panel) from left to right: Stephanie Moore and Kathi Lefebvre; Mike Parsons; Tim Davis and Harry Nelson. Bottom: Young students and mentors.

Fig. 2. Scenes from the ISSHA Auction during the 18th ICHA in Nantes, 2018

Fig. 3. Happy Japanese delegates after learning their bid to host the 20th ICHA (2022) was successful.

Fig. 4. Eminent ISSHA members being nominated Honorary Members during the 18th Conference. From left to right: Marta Estrada, Linda Medlin, Pat Tester, Robin Raine and Tim Wyatt.

of ISSHA for their years of service, in particular Gustaaf Hallegraeff, council and executive member since 2006, and strongly committed to the Publication and Dissemination Committee through the edition of conference proceedings and other website sections (trail-blazers, HAB art gallery and others), and L. MacKenzie and L. Proença for hosting the 16th ICHA (New Zealand) and 17th ICHA (Brazil) respectively. The new ISSHA Executive and Council for the 2018-2020 period is (new members in bold):

Executive

President: Vera Trainer (USA)
 Vice-Presidents:
 Wayne Litaker (USA)
 Po Teen Lim (Malaysia)
 Secretary: **Elin Lindehoff** (Sweden)
 Treasurer: **Nina Lundholm** (Denmark)
 Past-president: Beatriz Reguera (Spain)

Council Members

Ana Amorin (Portugal)
 Aurelia Tubaro (Italy)
 Christine Band-Schmidt (Mexico)

Esther Garcés (Spain)
 Ian Jenkinson (China, France)
Ingrid Sassenhagen (France, Germany)
 Keith Davidson (United Kingdom)
 Henrik Enevoldsen (Denmark)
Luis Mafra (Brazil)
Shauna Murray (Australia)
 Marta Estrada (Spain)
 Philipp Hess (France)
 Ichiro Imai (Japan)
Dedmer B. Van de Wall (Netherlands)
Steffaney Wood (Finland)

In addition, the Society established the “honorary member” figure, to include ISSHA members with outstanding contributions to HAB science and society and a retirement age who will be welcome to future conferences with a considerable discount in their registration fees.

Honorary members, **Marta Estrada, Linda Medlin, Pat Tester, Robin Raine** and **Tim Wyatt** were called to the stage during the Closing Ceremony and synopses of their biographies presented (Fig. 4).

The profiles of these honorary members can be found at <https://isssha.org/publications-resources/hab-trailblazers/> and those of the ISSHA officers and council members at <http://www.isssha.org/Society/ISSHA-Council-Members>

ISSHA Achievement Awards

Maureen Keller Student Presentation Awards

Best student oral presentation was awarded to **Marc Long** from University of Wollongong (UOW, Australia) and Université de Bretagne Occidentale (UBO, France) for his contribution, *A multi-trait approach reveals the physiologic impacts of Cu on Alexandrium minutum and their exudates.*

Marc obtained his Master’s degree in Marine Biology in 2015. In parallel with his university studies, Marc has been working on phytoplankton physiology and chemical ecology since 2011 in the laboratory of marine environmental studies (LEMAR, France) under the supervision of Dr. Hélène Hégaret and Dr. Philippe Soudant. During his studies, he also undertook research projects at the University of Wollongong (Australia) under the supervision of Professor D. Jolley and at the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA,

Marc Long
(Best Oral Presentation)

Northeast Fisheries Science Center, United States) in Milford Connecticut, studying phytoplankton physiology with Dr. Gary H. Wikfors.

The work presented at ICHA2018 was part of his Ph.D. research, revealing that toxic concentrations of Cu increased the allelochemical potency of *A. minutum* and that the release was related to physiological stress. Overall, this research highlighted a complex interplay between allelochemical interactions and abiotic factors.

Marc is currently submitting his Ph.D. thesis as a collaboration between the University of Wollongong (UOW, Australia) and the Université de Bretagne Occidentale (UBO, France). During his Ph.D. project, Marc characterized the allelochemical interactions between the toxic dinoflagellate *A. minutum* and the diatom *Chaetoceros muelleri*. His main interests are the bio-

logic interactions, chemical ecology and microalgal physiology.

Oral Presentation, Honorable Mention was awarded to **Juan Fernández Zabala's**: *Are macroalgae a reliable method for the quantification of BHABs*, co-authored with Emilio Soler-Onís, Ana Amorim and Fernando Tuya. Juan was born in the Basque Country, Spain. He studied Biology and Biochemistry at the University of Navarra, taking his last year at the University of Tromsø, Norway. During this year, Juan was involved in a project which aimed at the production of biosurfactants from marine hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria at the Norwegian College of Fishery Science. In 2013, he moved back to Spain where he obtained his master's degree in biotechnology at the Autonomous University of Madrid (UAM). The following year, Juan moved to the Canary Islands where he has been living for the past four years. During this time, he has been working at the Spanish Bank of Algae (BEA) as a flow-cytometry technician and participating in monitoring campaigns in the Canary Islands for BHAB risk assessment. Currently he is working on his PhD project in the framework of the European project MIMAR, supervised by Emilio Soler Onís, Ana Amorim and Rogelio Herrera at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). The main topic of his research is the ecology and bloom dynamics of BHAB dinoflagellates in the Macaronesian region. To

Océane Reale
(Best Poster Presentation)

address this, several methodologies are being developed to optimize sampling and cell collection and to study the distribution (both horizontal and vertical) of BHAB populations and how different biotic and abiotic factors contribute to this distribution. He is also interested in taxonomy of benthic dinoflagellates using both molecular and morphological approaches.

Océane Reale, Best Poster Presentation, a PhD Student at ANSES, Laboratory of Fougères (France) in Toxicology in vitro of Food Contaminants, received the award for her poster *In vitro toxicological assessment of lipophilic phycotoxins on Enteric Glial Cells*, co-authored by Valerie Fessard and Antoine Huguet. She is studying in the science agronomy engineering school (AgroCampus Ouest, Rennes, France) and specializing in Biotechnology for Health. She had the opportunity to do a 6-month internship in Montréal (Canada) in 2013-2014 in Biochemistry at the University of Quebec where she became fascinated with the world of research and experimentation. For her last internship and after her engineer diploma, she worked in the pharmaceutical industry at Servier (Biologie Servier, Gidy, France) in Preclinical Toxicology in vitro department as a scientific research associate. She worked on the development of 3D HepaRG cell models, a new tool for the evaluation of toxicity of new drugs. Captivated by the toxicology universe, she had the chance to work at ANSES (the French Agency for Food, Environment and Occupational Health and Safety) for a European Food Safety Authority project in genotoxicology evaluating the toxicity of two mycotoxins (Enniatin B and Beauvericin) using a mouse model.

Juan Fernández Zabala (Oral Presentation, Honorable Mention)
facing La Graciosa Island, his sampling area in northern Lanzarote, Canary Island

She continued her research in toxicology with a thesis project on the development of new cell models of the intestinal barrier (tri-culture and co-culture with epithelial cells, goblet cells and glial enteric cells), a tool for a best evaluation of toxicity of 6 phycotoxins. This thesis is supervised by Valerie Fessard and Antoine Huguet at ANSES Fougères.

Wai Mun Lum, *Poster Presentation, Honorable Mention*, from University of Tokyo, Japan, received the Maureen Keller award for the poster titled *Phylogenetic and morphological comparisons of Chattonella spp. collected from Southeast Asia* co-authored by Kazuya Takahashi, Garry Benico, Hong Chang Lim, Po Teen Lim, Chui Pin Leaw, Rhodora Azanza, Elsa Furio, Sandric Chee Yew Leong, Thaithaworn Lirdwitayaprasit, Hikmah Thoha and Mitsunori Iwataki. Born in Malaysia, she pursued Bachelor (with Honors) of Marine Science at the University of Malaysia, Sabah, Malaysia. Aiming to develop biosensors or chemical sensors for shellfish poisoning, she conducted her bachelor graduation research project entitled “Nanosensor based formaldehyde detection of narrow-barred Spanish mackerel”, under the supervision of Dr. Md. Shafiquzaman Siddiquee. However, she realized that extensive understanding of these harmful algae was necessary before developing such sensors. Thus, she is currently pursuing her Master’s degree at the University of Tokyo, Japan, su-

Wai Mun Lum
(Poster Presentation, Honorable Mention)

pervised by Dr. Mitsunori Iwataki, with the support of a Japanese Government (Monbukagakusho: MEXT) Scholarship. Through collaboration with several laboratories in Southeast Asia, she is studying the taxonomy of harmful raphidophytes species of the genus *Chattonella* as well as other marine harmful dinoflagellates in that region.

Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award

The *Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award 2016* was given to **Beatriz Reguera** for outstanding contributions to the biology and population dynamics of shellfish toxin-producing microalgae, in particular *Dinophysis* species (Fig. 5). These are low biomass HABs that even at densities of a few hundreds per litre, contaminate shellfish with diarrhetic shellfish poisons and cause lengthy shellfish harvesting closures in Atlantic

coastal waters in Europe. B. Reguera’s objective has been to obtain knowledge of species-specific differences (niche descriptions), mixotrophic behaviour and the physical-biological interactions driving the initiation, development and decline of *Dinophysis* populations in upwelling- influenced and stratified systems. Her work has informed conceptual models and contributed to the parameterization of biological processes for the development of predictive models in the framework of operational oceanography. Mainly based on field observations and laboratory incubations she explained the polymorphic life cycles and behaviour of *Dinophysis* species, showing that different small morphotypes labeled as separate taxons were but different stages of larger-sized *Dinophysis* species. Her research contributed to species-specific design of field sampling strategies to estimate physiological parameters of low-density *Dinophysis* populations in situ.

Beatriz has been a tireless mentor, promoter and communicator of HAB research by serving on numerous committees and panels. She hosted the highly successful 8th ICHA conference in Vigo in 1997, since 1992 served as the Spanish delegate to IPHAB which she chaired from 2002-2006, served two terms as ISSHA President (2008-2014), was member of the SCOR-IOC GEOHAB Scientific Steering Committee (2002-2006), chaired the ICES-IOC Working Group on HAB Dynamics (Chair 1992-1996), and currently is chief editor of the IOC-UNESCO newsletter *Harmful Algae News*

A short biography of her can be found at the *HAB Trail Blazers* section on the ISSHA website <https://issha.org/publications-resources/hab-trailblazers/beatrizreguera/>

Fig. 5. Beatriz Reguera receiving her award from Prof Yasumoto himself

Anna Godhe - In Memoriam

Anna Godhe passed away on April 4th 2019 after a strenuous fight with cancer.

Her untimely passing represents a big loss for the scientific community. We all remember her true passion for research, her important contributions to marine phytoplankton ecology and her open mind. She was always available to share knowledge and discuss with colleagues and students the fascinating mysteries of the life of unicellular organisms. Anna was a very positive person, a dedicated mentor of PhD students and post docs, and an excellent scientist.

Anna started her scientific career investigating the diversity and distribution patterns of dinoflagellate resting cysts along the Swedish coast. These studies provided an account of the different phytoplankton species that produce benthic resting stages in these coastal waters, explored the link between resting stage abundance and distribution and different environmental factors and provided the first evidence that many diatom and dinoflagellate resting stages are capable of long term (up to decades) survival in anoxic deep sediments. She tested the influence of benthic versus planktonic inocula on the development and composition of diatom communities with microcosm experiments demonstrating the importance of benthic resting stages and providing evidence for distinct species-specific life strategies.

Anna provided several valuable contributions on the use of molecular tools for the identification and quantification of phytoplankton species in the natural environment. The focus was the identification of harmful species, of resting stages in the sediments, and of cryptic species of the marine genus *Skeletonema*.

In recent years, the scientific interest of Anna has focussed on the marine diatom *Skeletonema marinoi*, which became a model for genetic and genomic studies. Microsatellite markers were used to investigate the population genetic structure of this diatom at various spatial and temporal scales along the Swedish coast and in the Baltic Sea, in collaboration with various colleagues.

The in-depth knowledge of the genetic profile of *S. marinoi*, together with the results of laboratory investigations on the intraspecific variability in physiological responses at different environmental conditions, set the premises for establishing this centric diatom as a model species for genomic research and for studies addressing the evolution and adaptations in unicellular microalgae. Anna promoted the whole genome sequencing of *Skeletonema marinoi* within the CEMEB consortium at the University of Gothenburg. The genome sequencing of this species and the establishment of various genomic tools that are in progress will allow investigation of the molecular bases of the biology and adaptive mechanisms of this species. Reviving natural populations from their dormant phase buried in core sediments offer a unique setting to study evolution in action in microalgae over a time scale that is not affordable with laboratory experimentation.

A part of Anna's research activity has been carried out at the University of Mangalore (India) within a collaboration with the University of Gothenburg.

This collaboration allowed to develop her favourite research themes in a different environmental setting, the tropical oligotrophic Arabian Sea.

Finally, it is with heavy hearts but in the spirit of Anna, that we add a personal note about Anna as a colleague and friend. The words we think about when we think about Anna are: enthusiastic, genuinely interested, open-minded, courageous, strong, ready to try new ways, excited of venturing into new territory, bridges disciplines, great collaborator, prefers complementing rather than competition, takes on challenges, not discouraged by failure, positive attitude, sees the potential rather than the problems, has opinions, limitless energy, and finally, an endlessly supportive and loyal friend.

Marina Montresor, Stazione Zoologica
Anthon Dorn, Napoli, Italy
Anke Kremp, Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea
Research, Warnemünde, Germany
Karin Rengefors, University of Lund, Sweden

Forthcoming events

ICHA 2020

19th ICHA October 11-16, 2020. La Paz, B.C.S. Mexico *Save the date!*

Registration will open during 2019. ISSHA members can register at special rates!

Participants wishing to receive the ISSHA member rate for conference registration must join ISSHA or renew their memberships prior to the 12th of June, 2020.

The 19th International Conference on Harmful Algae will take place from the 11th to the 16th of October 2020 at the Conference Center of La Paz, BCS, Mexico, being the 2nd ICHA conference held in Latin America. As the last conferences, the 2020 conference will include topics related with the understanding of the causes, evolution and impacts of harmful microalgae and cyanobacteria. We are planning an enjoyable meeting where scientists can present their research, share their ideas, establish new collaborations, and connect the science on harmful algae with the beneficiaries of this research.

Our reasons for holding this meeting are based on the recurrent presence

of Harmful Algal Blooms that have affected the economy and public health in various coastal regions and inland waters of Mexico. These events have been associated with the mortality of marine organisms such as free-living and farmed fish, dolphins, turtles and seabirds; as well as the presence of diverse phycotoxins in clams, oysters and mussels, which put people's health and lives at risk, reason for which it is necessary to establish sanitary closures for periods of weeks or months. Undoubtedly, this is a problem requiring collaboration efforts to reduce the adverse effects of these natural phenomena.

La Paz is an ideal city for the meeting where many academic institutes are found. It is a small, secure and quiet city, with beautiful surroundings, which is visited by many international tourists and academics year round. The average temperature in October is between 21 and 34 °C.

For some countries, a visa may be required. Please check visa regulations

well in advance with your local Mexican Consulate for official instructions on the specific visa regulations and application procedures.

As the major host of the conference, ISSHA will support the event with various activities: Travel awards to students and post-docs, several achievement awards, and ISSHA auction.

For more detailed information concerning the conference, please consult our web page www.icha2020.com

Looking forward to seeing you in La Paz, Mexico!

Dra. Christine J. Band Schmidt
On behalf of the Local Organizing Committee
IPN-CICIMAR

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 63:
September 1st 2019

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Lay-out

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**The publication of Harmful Algae News is sponsored
by the Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen**